

Relevance of On-line Office Administration through Working from Home in Future Education System

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ABSTRACT

The progress in informative communication technology (ICT) and internet technologies supported new innovative business models like e-business, e-education, and e-governance. It is expected that the developments in multimedia technology shifts the conventional higher education and training system completely into online ubiquitous education system. This helps the learner to study in any university located anywhere in the globe. Students get freedom to work and study simultaneously by enrolling online education in these global universities. When online education model is considered as next wave in higher education system, we propose a new idea of online office system to support online education model. This online office management system serves as back office system of present college based education system. This online office functions like conventional office system in higher education where it does all functions related to marketing, admission, enrollment, managing online study materials, online attendance, online assignment submission & evaluation management, handling student and faculty queries, supporting examination based evaluation and finally monitoring degree/diploma certificate generation. All these online office functions can be managed and controlled by a team of online office managers working from their homes so that the physical existence of the online global education providers/universities can be totally eliminated. This paper highlights the concept of online office back-up in ubiquitous higher education system, objectives of working from home model, its consequence in developing countries like India, its advantages to students, employees and service providers, benefits to all the stakeholders and the society, constraints for the employees and employers, and disadvantages to the stake holders due to such model. It is found that such model decreases the expenditure for travelling, to have better homely food etc. for the employees and decrease expenditure for office space and maintenance for employers/service providers.

Keywords: Ubiquitous online education, online back office, working from home model.

1. INTRODUCTION

Time and people will change automatically during the course of time. In olden days the education system was depending on teachers and other supporting staff members. There was no sign of computerization or automation. The teachers were using black board for teaching, the office staff members were using ledgers, files and papers and maintaining the documents manually. The advent of technology has brought changes drastically in both teaching and back office activities. Now teachers are using LCD projectors for teaching and get animated teaching aids with the help of internet. Assignments are given and evaluated online. Teachers keep upgrading themselves using the internet and they can teach the latest concepts in their subjects. In future days, all the assignments, presentations could be possible online, students may get the service using Laptop, Notepad, I-pad etc. In future education system, teachers could work at home and they may teach the subjects and give assignments sitting at home [1-2]. The examination scheme may be completely online based and computerized valuation system may replace the present manual paper valuation system. The future education system is becoming more and more tech savvy and most of the schools and colleges are obtaining better equipments like usage of computer system and electronic equipments etc to cope with this latest technology. This trend will help the teachers to work at home, saving a lot of time and increasing their work area with the advent of the technology. The students will be able to study by learning online, send their projects, assignments, essays through email to the teachers, they can work at home through computers/smart phones [3-4]. In this paper we have discussed an innovative concept of doing back office work from home using information communication technology. This paper highlights the concept of online office back-up in ubiquitous higher education system, objectives of working from home model, its consequences in developing countries like India, its advantages to students, employees, employers and

society, benefits to all the stakeholders and the society, constraints for the employees, employers and the society, and the disadvantages to the stake holders due to such model. It is found that such model decreases the expenditure for travelling, to have better homely food etc. for the employees and decrease expenditure for office space and maintenance for employers/service providers.

2. OBJECTIVES OF ONLINE EDUCATION SYSTEM IN FUTURE

Online Learning and the future of residential education is exchange of ideas about the future of higher education on-campus and off campus. Online education makes the development of new technologies and new practices. Computer will become more reliable and specialized. It will help the students for their online education. Students can send their assignments, Project reports and also can write their examination with their own wish through online. It is also studied that the ubiquitous online education system has many similar features of ideal education system in terms of the properties like global reachability, inelastic demand, open courses for everybody, high quality courses for everybody, minimum instructors requirement, low overhead, low investments, free of Government regulations, portability, satisfying everyone's intellectual needs, less time consumption, potential opportunity for high income, repeated opportunity for continuing education, ubiquity, technology dependent, all-round development through education, hundred percent efficiency, choice of alternative courses, and longer sustainability [4]. Using online conferencing as a tool students can interact between each other and with the faculty whom they wish to communicate on chosen subject. This is used in education system which facilitates the traditional class room based teaching using internet tools for both watching the lessons and interaction on a given subject. Online learning allows the students to continue to work while learning. The block diagram representing online education systems in terms of characteristics to support working at home is shown in Fig. 1.

3. FUTURE EDUCATION SYSTEM - INDIAN PERSPECTIVE

India is a developing country and is growing with leaps and bounds. India has reached a remarkable milestone in Technology and communication which are very much required for the future higher education system. The education sector is completely modernized with the initiation of online education. Many organization in India now provide online education with disciplines like, MBA, MCA, Executive MBA, Digital Marketing etc. Indian Govt. through its Ministry Human Resource Development and Dept. of Higher Education has developed objectives of higher education of the country to expand the Higher Education sector in all its modes of delivery to increase the Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) in Higher Education to 15% by 2011-12 to 21% by 2016-17 and 30% by the year 2020. To realize the objective the only solution is creation & supporting of online education opportunities in the country. Online education gives freedom to the students to work and study at the same time. The online study material can be used anytime and anywhere. To achieve this goal the supporting tool i.e., internet and mobile communication technology has reached considerable level of penetration in the country during last 10 to 15 years. The acceleration of internet growth in India can be gauged from the fact that India took 10 years to move from 10 to 100 million. It took 3 years to move from 100 to 200 million, whereas the next 100 million (from 200 to 300M) milestone was achieved in just 1 year. Even if the same growth is maintained, India will reach 500 million users before end of 2016. In comparison, China has around 650 million internet users accounting for around 43% of their population. United States has roughly 279 million users accounting for roughly 47 percent of their population. With 302 million internet users by end of December 2014, India has overtaken United States as the second largest country in the world in terms of number of internet users with penetration of around 24 percent. It is found that the healthy growth in internet users has been driven by rural Indians who are now increasingly accessing internet either on their mobile phones or computers. Rural India registered a growth rate of 39 percent to reach 101 million users by October 2014, whereas urban India grew by 29 percent to reach 177 million by October 2014. By end of December 2014, Urban India had 190 million internet users (63%), while rural India had 112 million (37%). It is predicted that 52 million new internet users will be added in first six months of 2015, means that India will be adding roughly 10 million internet users every month. In terms of frequency of internet usage in India, about 61 percent of users are daily users. About 18 percent access internet several times a day, 10 percent users at least once a day and 33 percent access on all 7 days. It is also found that most of the users access internet for general search, social networking browsing and entertainment. Interestingly 61 percent access internet for online shopping and 63 percent access to do online transactions [5].

In India, the usage of mobile phone to for communication and internet access is also growing in an accelerated manner. Presently around 173 million or 57 percent of Indian internet users access internet from their mobile phones. The percent of mobile internet users has grown more rapidly than traditional broadband users. 49 million new mobile internet users have been added between Oct 2013 to Oct 2014. Out of 125 crores population, about 90 crores mobile phone users are registered and more than 90% young population is using mobile phones for their regular communication. Such tremendous growth of mobile phone users and internet users through mobile devices in India is surely shows a great sign for expanded opportunity for online education and working from home model in India.

Figure 1: The future education system which supports working at home.

4. WORKING FROM HOME MODEL

The online education system provides flexibility for students and supporting staff members to work from anywhere and not only they can concentrate on their work but also they can do different activities including earning degrees in higher education. Working from home is a type of flexible method of working sitting at home doing the same work presently the staff members and students do in the traditional class room based study [6-7]. This requires an agreement between employer and employee regarding the nature of work, working hour, service regulations and salary and other commitments. working hours, working part time etc. It is a challenge to both employers and employees.

As per the technology acceptance model proposed by Lin and Wu (2002) [8], the use of a new model in society depends on peoples behavioral intention to use which in turn depends on attitude towards use, which further depends on perceived usefulness, perceived cost, perceived assurance and perceived ease of use [6]. The most basic proposition of the modified technology acceptance model called TCSET model is Users Stimulation (SC) and is a function of Stimulative Behavior (SB) and Stimulative Intention(SI) [9].

Figure 2 : Working from home model : Future impact of IT in education system.

Perceived Usefulness depends on : (1) Ubiquitous service, (2) Enhanced Productivity, (3) Time saving, (4) Opportunity for better service, (5) Status in the Society, and (6) Challenging. Perceived Ease of Use depends on : (1) Easy Operation of the device, (2) Easy and simple method of obtaining service, (3) Bundled services, (4) Availability of services, & Network, (5) Ease of switching between new and old models, (6) Ease of making corrections, (7) Ease of Registration to the bank. Perceived Cost depends on : (1) Low device cost, (2) Low service cost, (3) Avoiding intermediaries, (4) Low transaction cost, (5) Low cost registration for availing service, (6) Zero hidden cost. Perceived Assurance depends on : (1) Security of customer and Information, (2) Accuracy of transaction information, (3) Reliability of service [10-11].

Working from home model for online ubiquitous education using information communication technology is shown in Fig. 2. The advantages, disadvantages, benefits and constraints of this model are identified and analysed in terms of stakeholders frame of reference. The basic proposition of the modified technology acceptance model which include Users Stimulation (SC) and is a function of Stimulative Behavior (SB) & Stimulative Intention (SI) are also applicable with some modifications. The acceptance of this model by various stakeholders in the society depends on the critical factors like Cost reduction, Communication effectiveness, Ubiquitous connectivity, Time saving, Flexibility of service, Freedom of choice & work, and Personal Satisfaction etc. The user stimulation constructs like Advantages, Benefits, Constraints and Disadvantages in terms of identified factors are important in deciding the adaption of such model in higher education system. These constructs will also decides the Stimulative Behavior and Stimulative Intention of using such model.

5. NEED FOR WORKING FROM HOME

Working from home literally means working at your home to earn a satisfactory living, whether you have an office or not. Working from home is a popular family-friendly, sustainable working practice that offers a potential solution to many of today's pressing problems faced by the employers as well as employees. A work from home or work at home model involves working from home and is differs from the tele-working that it does not require the employee stay electronically connected to the work location during business hours. It can also mean work at home opportunities that pays you big bucks to do data entry work. Here work performed is generally done independently so does not require team interaction or consistent communication. Work at home indicates that an employee or contractor can complete work duties within their own home. It also is more likely that the employee can live far from the actual location of his/her business area for which he or she is working because face to face contact at the location may not be necessary. But it is least known fact that the home-based workforce is practiced in different parts of the country and abroad. Work homes are not just a place of work producing avenues, also they can be found throughout the history, usually

recognized as workplaces having some motive [6-7]. The various factors contributing under the four identified constructs like advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages are derived by a qualitative data collection instrument namely focus group method [12-13], in the point of view of the employees, the employers, the students and the society and depicted in the following sections.

6. ADVANTAGES OF FUTURE EDUCATION SYSTEM THOUGH WORKING FROM HOME

By working at home people can save their precious time which they normally spend in going to the workplace and return to home from the workplace. In addition to this they can save many hidden costs associated like costs of commuting, car wear and tear, fuel, road taxes, parking as well as indirect costs such as expensive professional wardrobes and the dry-cleaning of those. Often they can also save on older children's care arrangements although for younger children it is highly inadvisable to forgo the childcare arrangement and try to balance close care and supervision with the demands of the job [14-15].

6.1 Advantages for Employees

1. Reduces the Working Time : Working time include times like commuting, waiting etc., along with working in a situated office. The employees have to travel from home to their office surpassing heavy traffic. This is a strenuous job and involves more time to reach the office and work over there. Working from home will reduce the working hours, thus maintains balance in demand & supply of labor market and it also will reduce the work week, vacation time and earlier retirement. Short hour lifestyles allow people to build stronger social connections and maintain their physical and mental health.

2. Confident Work without supervision : Employees working from home can plan their work well in advance. They are the sole supervisors for themselves for the work carried out by them. There is no interference of fellow employees, boss etc. Hence they can carry out their work without being disturbed by others.

3. Family and Health Care : Working in a family environment is fruit bearing and healthy also. While working in home employees feel convenience and can work in a friendly environment with family members. When employees work from home, they have more flexibility in terms of managing their time thus getting more convenient working environment. They can also get rid of hidden costs and they have fewer distractions from inmates but no destructions from coworkers. Moreover, when they work from home, they have better work-life balance and hence can be healthier.

6.2. Advantages for Employers

1. Conducting Regular Meeting : If Employer conducts regular meeting online, essential information related to the business can be shared regularly and this can help the employees to keep in touch with the rest of the colleagues and other stakeholders.

2. Providing Flexible Schedule : In online working model, employers provides the suitable time schedule to the employees round the clock so that the employees can choose their shift depending on their convenience which increases their motivation and efficiency in work.

3. Increased Productivity : Studies show that staffers who work from home are more productive than those who work in a typical office environment. Employees working at home have greater autonomy, face fewer interruptions and can focus on their work. This in turn increases the productivity of the organization

6.3 Advantages for Students & Teachers

1. Laptop and Computer Facilities : Students who would like to work/study from home should possess a laptop. They can work by using their laptops with internet facility. Data gathered may be fed into the computer and can be converted into information. The information in the form of assignment, online examination answers may be sent to the organization/university via internet by sitting at home.

2. Online Learning : Students can find online schools offering education in their interested /specialized area irrespective on geographical boundaries.

3. Innovation Techniques in Teaching & Learning : The education system though working from home makes the teachers creativity, i.e., it will take a great deal of creative effort to bring out the most creative thinking in the classes. Teaching techniques and strategies continue to evolve. The role of a teacher has changed as well, from someone who conveys information to someone who facilitates student learning in a variety of ways. New technologies have also impacted teaching and learning approaches. Engaging students in their own learning can take many different forms and some of the most effective teachers employ a variety of techniques and strategies.

6.4 Advantages for the Society

1. Full Time Service : Working from home provides any time services to the people of the society. An individual who would like to utilize a particular service from an organization can avail that service at any time round the clock. For example, customer care services provide 24 hours service to the public.

2. Self Disciplined and Self Motivated Workers : Working from home will motivate people. People with self motivation can find a challenge in their work and they will complete the task. Working from home needs a lot of dedication, self-control and discipline to motivate ourselves to persevere in working at home alone over the long run without succumbing to the distractions and losing drive and momentum. Often a partial arrangement where workers report the office once or twice a week is the optimal arrangement as it allows for close interaction with colleagues and supervisors and ensures them remain in touch with the office developments while still permitting them the comfort and convenience of working from home.

3. Lesser stress & Depression : If the people are working as a full time employees in the office, it will be more stressful whereas working from home will help them avoid the stress & depression and also will reduce the travelling irritation and traffic jam, sound pollution etc. Working from home also avoids other stresses like unfriendly coworkers, constant distractions etc.

7. BENEFITS OF FUTURE EDUCATION SYSTEM THOUGH WORKING FROM HOME

7.1 Benefits for Employees

1. Convenient timings and flexible schedule : With a suitable office management software, employees can do work from the computer in their home connected to internet with a minimum investment. This flexibility cannot be achieved, if they are working in the office.

2. Quiet & homely atmosphere : The employees who work from home are having comfortable environment and are given a free access to the work to be completed. Since there are no disturbances from fellow employees etc. a person working from home can work in a quite atmosphere without being disturbed by outsiders.

3. Saving travel expenses : A person working in an office needs to travel to his work place and return back home daily after travelling a long distance. He has to spend considerable money from his pocket and also waste considerable time for commuting from home.

7.2 Benefits for Employers

1. Saving office space and maintenance expenses : Working from home model helps employers to save investment on infrastructure work space and makes employees to work from their home thus saving his precious time and money.

2. Improvement on human resource management : Employers are using technology in the workplace for recruitment and training. It speed-up the process of screening, recruiting and hiring new employees. The all process saves time and makes the work easier. Technology can also be used to track performance and productivity of each employee at work. Once employee are aware that they are monitored, their productivity will increase.

3. High morale, efficiency & profit : Employees with flexible work options often have higher morale and enjoy their job responsibilities more than those in a traditional office environment. Increased morale often has a positive impact on quality of work and productivity, which benefits the business in terms of bottom-line earnings in turn increases the profit of the organization.

7.3. Benefits for Students & Teachers

1. Innovations : This method helps to identify the most effective teaching techniques and encourage the innovations. Teachers with the help of animations can create virtual reality during teaching difficult subjects like computer architecture, Operating system, microprocessors and any management or technical subjects. Importance can be given to various innovations which vary and are different from teacher to teacher.

2. Opportunity for online communication : Instructors can be more approachable in the online setting. Students may feel more comfortable talking openly with their teachers through online chats, emails and newsgroup discussions through video channels rather than face-to-face. Online correspondence need not wait for office hours that may not be convenient for both Teachers and students.

3. Ease of Accessibility : Course work of the study can be accessible for students when they need it. Students can review lectures, discussions, interactions and comments. Students can also share notes with each other to help & facilitate online learning.

7.4 Benefits for the Society

1. Low infrastructure investment : Since the work is done from home the cost of maintaining the infrastructure required for the office is reduced which in turn reduces infrastructural requirement in the society.

2. Better security to women in work life : Employees working from home may not have disturbance from other fellow employees. He/she feels comfortable at home while carrying out his office work. This has added advantage for women employees in developing countries where social security for women is at stake.

3. Gender equality in choice of work : This facility of choice of work is useful to both male and female employees who would like to work from home. They can select the work as per their interest and competency without external constraints.

8. CONSTRAINTS OF FUTURE EDUCATION SYSTEM THOUGH WORKING FROM HOME

8.1 Constraints for Employees

1. Loss of self confidence : Employees working from home are not working face to face with employer, sometimes they will not get proper guidance, it will lose the self confidence of the employee.

2. Distractions at home : While there are distractions in the office because of coworkers, the distractions of working from home are much different. We can get distracted from our neighbours, kids or other family members. Employees need to make sure that they understand that they are actually working and they are unavailable when they are working from home. When the ladies are planning to work from home they will be having the additional distractions like laundry, washing the dishes, taking care of the small children etc. When family members are at home, the distractions will be more and can make working difficult.

3. Reduced interpersonal relationship : While working in a group employer and employee should identify each other. But here employees are communicate through phone, email, video conferencing and online messages tools, this types of communication eliminates the face to face communication. It makes the employees more reserved and self centered, they get buried into their work which can be of great harm to a business.

8.2 Constraints for Employers

1. Loss of control on employees : Here employers are not abide by a proper rules and laws of the organization. Employees will take their own decisions while following the rules and work will be done following employees own ideas. It will misuse the cost and income of the business. If there are proper rules or laws while working between employer and employee it will become successful in all the ways.

2. Inadequate supervision : Managers may find it difficult to manage the home workers than managing staff in the office. It can be a challenging factor for most of the managers who may not come face-to-face with the staff working from home. Since there is no proper person to monitor the work being carried out at home there may be a fear of getting the things done in a most accomplished manner. Lack of trust is also another factor which can be the biggest barrier to achieve a successful home working. They should make sure the employee knows what is expected of him and what he is expected to do by sharing information and ideas with his boss and colleagues.

3. Uncertainty in achievement of target : An employee who works from home sets a time frame and deadline for the most his important projects. He will be also very thorough about the length of time he will take to finish a particular job. When employees are working from home they will be distracted from so many factors like neighbours entry in the middle and involving in unnecessary discussions with them, family matters, mobile conversations with relatives etc. may take away the work you intended and there is a fear of non completion of work in a stipulated time. As much as people work to carefully schedule their time, there is always a chance that something will come up that can throw a light in their future plans. This can happen to anyone regardless of whether on their working days spent in the office or at the time of working from home. In both the cases the key to successfully resolving the issue is communication. Such risk is always there for employers in working from home model.

8.3 Constraints for Students & Teachers

1. Quality of service becomes weak : Online studies provides weak services to the students there is no proper communication between teachers and students and sometimes if is there any technical problem comes they will not possible to give proper training to the students.

2. Immediate solution to the problem is not possible : Online classes do not offer the same immediate and regular access to instructors and classmates as traditional face-to-face classes. The communication typically takes place through e-mail and in virtual discussion forums. While this can aid in learning technology, it negatively impacts a student's ability to interact with professors, ask questions and get immediate help. It also takes away from some of the social and team-building that occurs informally in college classrooms.

3. Time commitment : Students sometimes misconstrue that online classes require less time and effort than traditional courses. Students who struggle with traditional course rigor often have difficulty with the time commitment required for online class work. Teachers have to give schedule time each day to read assignments and complete quizzes and tests that would take in class in a traditional setting. Online students also have to engage in class discussions and complete assignments, papers and projects. Team activities may also add to the time commitment in some classes, as students must often communicate with peers electronically and collaborate on work.

8.4 Constraints for the Society

1. Tendency for idle work accumulation : Working from home provides idle services to the society. It makes the laziness and wasting time of the employer and employees. If employees are provided with fulltime services, they will not make use of the working natures.

2. Uncomfortable due to reduced social interactions : There may not be suitable space at home for employees working from home. If the working space is smaller, it makes the people uncomfortable to enter the working area and it is difficult to take proper discussions of a business.

3. Reduction in economic activities : Due to restricted daily movement of the people for their office jobs, the business & economic activities depending on commuting gets affected.

9. DISADVANTAGES OF FUTURE EDUCATION SYSTEM THOUGH WORKING FROM HOME

9.1 Disadvantages for Employees

1. Decreased chance to get promotion : When employees are out of sight, they can be out of mind as well. Therefore, their boss may forget them and they can be overlooked for promotion. However, they can avoid this situation with regular office visits such as once or twice a week. By these visits, they can remind themselves to their co-workers and especially to their boss and prove their dedications to their career.

2. High self motivation required : When employees are working from home, they will not have a boss standing on top of their shoulder and waiting for them to finish that report. While not everyone needs a boss like this to finish their tasks by the deadline, they still need to have a lot of self discipline and motivation to always stay on top of their to-do list.

3. Continuous work, Doesn't end : Working from home, there are a lot of disadvantages to be faced by the employee. Since there is no-one looking over their shoulder enforcing strict hours they may feel tempted to work endlessly. This pressure to work endlessly may be compounded by the fact that they feel there are greater expectations made of them as a home-worker or by self-imposed pressures to prove themselves and their abilities in this arrangement. Moreover the employers and employees lack of physical separation between home and work make this pressure to work endlessly.

4. Less Social Interaction : An office is a workplace where employees can meet with other people, socialize and chit-chat. However, when they work from home, they have less social interaction. In work from home model, employees generally interact with others through phone or video conference. Therefore, they may start to feel loneliness thus the social life in working from home becomes only a dream. This can result in mild depression that pushes us to abandon their home employment and to rejoin the office environment.

9.2 Disadvantages for Employers

1. Difficulties to monitor employees, development and upgrading skills : Working from home there is lots of employees are working under one employer, this makes difficulty to monitor the employer about employees skills, knowledge, development, over time work etc. it makes the employee quit the company and they may go for other companies, this will reduces the demand of the employer.

2. Alienated from daily company developments : There is lot of changes from day today in a company and it may find difficulties to the employers which is important development of staff changes, new business, changes in company direction, new competitive, Intelligence of the employees etc.

9.3 Disadvantages for Students & Teachers

1. Students may feel isolated from the instructor and classmates : Anyone who worked in an office or any other workplace becomes accustomed to chatting with coworkers, discussing work project and other aspects of the workplace, while in a online learning students may feel isolate alone at home. Isolation can make the students mild depression.

2. Instructor may not always be available when students are studying or need help : students and teachers are not available always, some teachers may engage with some other work, students have wait for their need. It will wasting the students time and reduces the learning skill.

3. Online system is not ideal for all Learners : All the candidates are not ideal candidate for online learning. If any students have problems with motivation, weak mind and it needs lots of individual attention from a teacher. Students have to think long and hard before joining the online learning programme.

9.4 Disadvantages for the Society

1. Internet error : If any technical problem arises like internet, software etc employers and employees cannot provide proper services to the society, until the problem is resolved.

2. Risk of Information and security problems : There are lots of risk information and security problems faced by the society through working from home software and communication systems. There are chances of misusing the transaction while working online.

3. It suits only some jobs not all : All the work cannot be done through online, only some of the remote jobs can be done.

10. CONCLUSION

A systematic business model named "working from home" is developed. The advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages of this model in the frame of reference of employees, employers, students/teachers and society are discussed. As more and more professionals seek a better work-life balance and more institutions adopt flexible policies to accommodate shifting workplace priorities and realities the working from home option is becoming increasingly viable. Employees see this as an ideal means to remain in the work force while enjoying all the advantages of being based at home. However the option has its potential advantages as well as hindrances. By working at home employees save on many hidden costs associated with going to work. It is more flexible and less distracted towards outside world. Stress involved is less when compared to office atmosphere and desired output may achieved. Since the stress involved is minor which leads to better health, one can lead a balanced life. At the same time there are some hindrances involving this system. One can get isolated since he is working at the same place. The worker may get attracted from

familial matters when working at home which leads to lesser concentration towards work. The worker may not get benefits, perks, promotions etc. which are prevailing in the office atmosphere. On the whole it may be concluded that "it is an option mostly preferred by women who need to juggle between home and work. But it shouldn't be a norm and should be allowed in special circumstances only. While working from home works for many people, there are some who also think that it's no fun and it gets too difficult to combat distractions. It is tough to draw a line or maintain a balance between work and home. When employees are working at their home, their work lacks proper focus as compared to while working atmosphere of a well disciplined office. Working from home isn't just easy on the employee, but the environment as well. If they are constantly at home working, they don't see the need to connect with their colleagues. This strains their relationship with their colleagues. Working from home teaches the employees management skills and to work and learn independently. But the onus is on the employers to try and make it a reliable activity for the employed. From the students point of view, availing higher education online provides an opportunity to save time, money and allows them to get desired education at any time allowing to work & earn while learning. Teachers can effectively utilize their time and provide service to anybody interested irrespective of geographical locations. The society gets maximum benefits by this 'working from home' model due to achievement of ideal system characteristics including low cost ubiquitous service from/to various stakeholders in an organization. This also improves the working environment and decreases the environmental pollution directly and indirectly. It is found that, in general such model decreases the expenditure for travelling, to have better homely food etc. for the employees and decrease expenditure for office space and maintenance for employers/service providers.

References

- [1] Bhattacharya, Shrayana. Maryada, "Membership and Minimum Wage: Collective Action and Intra-Household Relations". Asian Journal of Women's Studies. Vol. 16, No. 1, pp 7-41, 2010.
- [2] Edwards, N. Linda and Elizabeth Field-Hendrey. "Home-Based Work and Women's Labor Force Decisions." Journal of Labor Economics, Vol. 20, No. 1, pp. 170-199, 2002.
- [3] P. S. Aithal and Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, "Ideal education system and its realization through online education model using mobile devices", Proceedings of IISRO Multi Conference 2014, Bangkok, ISBN No. 978-81-927104-33-13, pp. 140 - 146, 2014.
- [4] P. S. Aithal & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, "An Innovative Education Model to realize Ideal Education System", International Journal of scientific research and management (IJSRM), Vol. 3, Issue 3, pp. 2464 - 2469, March, 2015.
- [5] IAMAI Digital Commerce Report 2014, Internet Mobile Association Of India (IAMAI) downloaded from website <http://www.iamai.in> on 30/03/2015.
- [6] Gopal, Meena, "In Demand in a Globalised World: Women Home Based Workers," Samyukta : a Journal of Women's Studies, Vol. 5, No. 1, pp 135-146, 2005.
- [7] Prugl, Elisabeth, "The Global Construction of Gender: Home Based Work in The Political Economy of the 20th Century", New York: Columbia University Press, 1999.
- [8] Lin, C.S and Wu, S., (2002) 'Exploring the Impact of Online Service Quality on Portal Site Usage', Proceeding of the 35th Hawaii International Conference on Systems Science, Hawaii, USA.
- [9] P. S. Aithal & K.V.M. Varambally, Security Issues in Online Financial Transactions with Special Reference to Banking Industry, Quality in Service Sector and Managerial Challenges – Allied Publisher Pvt. Ltd. 2006, pp. 103- 114. ISBN 81-7764-992-2.
- [10] P. S. Aithal, <http://www.arraydev.com/commerce/JIBC/K.V.M. Varambally>, Technological Management and Mobile Business Services in India – A Futuristic Approach Proceedings of International Conference in 10th South Asian Management Forum 2009 on "Change and Continuity : Management Prospects and Challenges" Organized by Royal Institute of Management, Bhutan. Page : 121 -139, ISBN: 978-99936-626-1-7, 2009
- [11] [11] K.V.M. Varambally and P.S. Aithal, Mobile Business Technology and Business Proliferation of Banks – A futuristic Approach Amity Business Review – an Indian Journal, 10, 1, Jan-June 2009, pp. 9 – 25, ISSN 0972-2343.
- [12] E. M. Rogers, 'Diffusion of Innovation', 1995, The Free Press, NY.
- [13] R. M. Morgan, and S. D. Hunt, 'The commitment-trust theory of relationship marketing', Journal of Marketing, Vol. 58, (July), pp. 20–38, 1994.
- [14] Sudarshan, M. Ratna, "Navigating Income Disparities: Home Based Workers and Production Chains." The India Economy Review, IIPM Think Tank, Vol. 4, Quarterly Issue, pp. 1-27, May 30, 2007.
- [15] Unni, Jeemol and Uma Rani. 2009. "Do Economic Reforms Influence Home-based Work in India ? Evidence from India." Special Issue on Inequality, Development and Growth, Feminist Economics, Vol. 15, No. 3, 2009, pp 191-225.

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